

Understanding the Geographical and Temporal Evolution of Asian Hate in the United States

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AGENDA

- Background
- Literature Review
- Research Motivation and Research Questions
- Research Methods
- Findings
- Conclusions and Future Work

Background

BACKGROUND

- Discrimination due to **arbitrary** differences has been around for a very long time
 - Anti-Asian hate crimes is one of the many forms of discrimination, but is not very **well studied**¹
- Due to the origin of Covid-19 being from China, there has been a **negative stigma** against Asians for bring the pandemic to the Americas
 - Even the US ex-president Donald Trump has called Covid-19 the “Chinese Virus” more than 20 times between March 16 and March 30 during 2020² (The Conversation)
- This has resulted in an **increase** in the amount of hate crimes, particularly against Asians³ (CTV News)

BACKGROUND

- On March 16th, 2020, several teens **vandalized** a store in Chinatown at San Francisco³ (Hrw.org)
- Additionally, a survey performed by the University of Toronto has shown that 11% of respondents have been **the target of some sort discrimination**

Literature Review

LITERATURE REVIEW

- One study of over 30 million tweets from 2015-2018 has shown that living in states with higher than 10% negative sentiment from analysis on the tweets is correlated with **higher amounts of inequality** in income and jobs⁹ (Science Direct)
- A book has been published about the geography of hate and how certain regions in the US are **more prone to hate crimes**¹⁰ (Spaces of Hate)
- Alternatively, studies in the past have also focused on how politics are **related to hate crimes** and how politicians differ in reactions to these crimes¹¹ (Sagepub)

LITERATURE REVIEW

- A study by the Pew Research Center has shown that there has been **increased discrimination** against African Americans and Asians during the pandemic⁶ (PEW Social Trends)
- A different study has investigated in the **discrimination and well-being** among Asians in America on Social Media during Covid-19⁷ (Rapid Communications)
- Other studies have done more research towards the **mental health** aspect of Asians during the pandemic⁸ (Psycnet)

Research Method

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What is the correlation between the number of Asian people and the amount of anti-Asian hate crimes?
2. How does the amount of anti-Asian hate crimes vary geographically?
3. How does the level of Asian hate compare to hate crimes against other demographics during the pandemic?

DATASETS USED

- FBI dataset from 1991 to 2018¹²
- NYPD dataset from 2019-2020¹³
- Asian population percentage, by state¹⁴ (US Census)
- Total population of each state¹⁵ (US Census)

	INCIDENT_ID	DATA_YEAR	ORI	PUB_AGENCY_NAME	PUB_AGENCY_UNIT	AGENCY_TYPE_NAME	STATE_ABBR	STATE_NAME	DIVISION_NAME
0	3015	1991	AR0040200	Rogers	NaN	City	AR	Arkansas	West South Central
1	3016	1991	AR0290100	Hope	NaN	City	AR	Arkansas	West South Central
2	43	1991	AR0350100	Pine Bluff	NaN	City	AR	Arkansas	West South Central
3	44	1991	AR0350100	Pine Bluff	NaN	City	AR	Arkansas	West South Central
4	3017	1991	AR0350100	Pine Bluff	NaN	City	AR	Arkansas	West South Central
...
201398	466130	2018	WV0540100	Parkersburg	NaN	City	WV	West Virginia	South Atlantic
201399	466159	2018	WV0540100	Parkersburg	NaN	City	WV	West Virginia	South Atlantic
201400	508677	2018	WV0540200	Vienna	NaN	City	WV	West Virginia	South Atlantic
201401	463503	2018	WVWSP2400	State Police:	Madison	State Police	WV	West Virginia	South Atlantic
201402	544359	2018	WVWSP3300	State Police:	Parkersburg	State Police	WV	West Virginia	South Atlantic

PROCESS FLOW CHART

Findings

RESEARCH QUESTION 2

Q: How does the amount of anti-Asian hate crimes vary geographically?

A: Anti-Asian crimes tend to propagate from more populated regions to less populated regions.

Sources: US
Population data,
FBI hate crime
dataset

RESEARCH QUESTION 3

Q: How does the level of Asian hate compare to hate crimes against other demographics during the pandemic?

A: Despite the increasing anti-Asian bias fueled by social media during the pandemic, the frequency of anti-Asian crimes was not as high as people thought.

Conclusion

Conclusion

Number of Felonies vs. Misdemeanors of Anti-Asian Offences in 2020

LIMITATIONS/FUTURE WORK

- Datasets used: We often lacked information on hate crimes in other states as well as in specific time ranges
- Establish a correlation between events and their causes on hate crime rates
- Establish a correlation instead of just a comparison between different targeted demographics
- Gather information on aspects of the perpetrators in addition to the victims of hate crime

REFERENCES

- ¹ <https://www.cbsnews.com/news/the-painful-history-of-anti-asian-hate-crimes-in-america/>
- ² <https://theconversation.com/donald-trumps-chinese-virus-the-politics-of-naming-136796>
- ³ <https://www.ctvnews.ca/canada/reports-of-anti-asian-hate-crimes-are-surging-in-canada-during-the-covid-19-pandemic-1.5351481>
- ⁴ <https://www.hrw.org/news/2020/05/12/covid-19-fueling-anti-asian-racism-and-xenophobia-worldwide>
- ⁵ <https://www.utoronto.ca/news/anti-asian-discrimination-rise-canada-u-t-researchers-find>
- ⁶ https://www.pewsocialtrends.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/3/2020/07/PSDT_07.01.20_racism.covid_Full.Report.pdf
- ⁷ <https://www.liebertpub.com/doi/full/10.1089/cyber.2020.0394>
- ⁸ <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2020-77454-001>
- ⁹ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352827321000252>
- ¹⁰ <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9780203952771-8/introduction-spaces-hate-geographies-discriminatio>
- ¹¹ <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/136248060200600408>
- ¹² <https://crime-data-explorer.fr.cloud.gov/pages/home>
- ¹³ <https://app.powerbigov.us/view?r=eyJrIjojYjg1NWl3YjgtYzkyOS00Nzc0LTkwMDAtNTgzM2I2M2JmYWWE1liwidCI6IjJiOWY1N2ViLTc4ZDEtNDZmYi1iZTgzLWEyYWZkZDdjNjA0MyJ9>
- ¹⁴ <https://worldpopulationreview.com/state-rankings/asian-population>
- ¹⁵ <https://www.infoplease.com/us/states/state-population-by-rank>